

Treatment ^b	Iron content (ppm)				Manganese content (ppm)				Rice yield (g/pot, 6 plants)	
	NH ₄ OAc, pH 4.8		NH ₄ OAc, pH 3.0		Exch. Mn NH ₄ OAc, pH 7		Reducible Mn NH ₄ OAc, pH 7 + 0.2% hydroquinone		Grain	Straw
	8d	15 d	8d	15 d	8d	15 d	8d	15 d		
Cal, FYM, Dry	2.5	2.5	4.1	4.1	1.0	1.0	290	290	7.65	36.80
Cal, FYM, Sat	5.7	7.5	7.4	19.6	7.0	10.5	277	270	12.25	47.60
Cal, FYM, Subm	7.0	9.2	24.7	36.5	9.5	15.0	266	252	19.47	56.00
Cal, no FYM, Dry	2.5	2.5	4.1	4.1	1.0	1.0	290	290	3.85	33.30
Cal, no FYM, Sat	3.7	6.0	7.9	13.6	3.2	7.7	282	277	8.93	44.60
Cal, no FYM, Subm	6.2	8.0	21.4	25.2	4.7	12.1	277	257	16.42	50.60
Noncal, FYM, Dry	4.0	4.0	5.9	5.9	1.8	1.8	312	312	8.15	38.20
Noncal, FYM, Sat	6.2	10.2	19.3	21.2	9.5	14.5	297	287	15.00	47.40
Noncal, FYM, Subm	7.2	10.3	46.9	52.0	13.0	19.0	287	277	20.90	59.40
Noncal, no FYM, Dry	4.0	4.0	5.9	5.9	1.8	1.8	312	312	7.12	37.40
Noncal, no FYM, Sat	5.0	8.7	17.9	17.9	5.0	10.5	303	285	9.60	41.00
Noncal, no FYM, Subm	7.0	9.5	26.7	36.0	8.1	15.5	292	280	15.85	48.90

^a Mean of 2 replications. ^b Cal= calcareous, FYM = farmyard manure, Sat = saturated, Subm = submerged.

sowing moisture from dry to submergence, and with the duration of moisture treatment (see table). Soil saturation and submergence 15 days before sowing resulted in a greater release of exchangeable Fe and Mn, which might be due to reduced conditions (Eh reduced from 530 to 260 mV in calcareous soil and from 510 to 256 mV in noncalcareous soil) and decrease in pH (from 8.2 to 7.6 in calcareous soil and from 8.1 to 7.8 in noncalcareous soil). Noncalcareous soil

recorded higher exchangeable Fe and Mn than calcareous soil. The addition of farmyard manure resulted in higher content of exchangeable Fe and Mn. The highest exchangeable Fe and Mn were observed under the presowing soil submergence treatment with farmyard manure.

Easily reducible Mn, however, showed a reverse trend. It rapidly decreased as a result of presowing moisture regimes with the addition of farm-

yard manure, which was accompanied by an increase in exchangeable Mn.

An increase in rice grain and straw yield was observed. It probably was due to an increase in the supply of Fe and Mn in the soil as a result of soil water treatments 15 days before sowing. The highest grain and straw yield was obtained in noncalcareous soil under presowing submergence treatment with addition of farmyard manure. ■

Population of the weed *Marsilia quartrifoliata* in plots with azolla

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Aduthurai, India

Irrigation water is usually released from Mattur reservoir in June in Thanjavur district. The first short-duration crop in the double-crop wetland system is planted in June-July. In the single-cropped wetland area, long-duration varieties are planted in September-October, 2-3 months after water is released. Submergence of those fields during that period encourages some wetland weeds such as *Marsilia quartrifoliata*, *Panicum repens*, *P. colonum*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Pistia striotus*, and *Echinochloa colona*. *M. quartrifoliata* spreads quickly and manual labor to remove it from the field before planting costs US\$41-103/ha.

At PES, fields where azolla was growing differed in *Marsilia* weed population from fields with no azolla. Weed population was assessed in 10 randomly selected areas, 10 m² each, in which azolla grew densely and in which azolla was absent. The weights follow:

Plots	Mean fresh weed wt (kg/10 m ²)
With dense azolla growth	0.52
Control (no azolla)	26.31

Trials on seed requirements showed that a minimum of 1 t seed material/ha was needed for the samba fields. Azolla can be grown without phosphorus application if the old water is drained from the field once a week and fresh water is maintained at 5-10 cm.

Thus a thick layer of azolla can ward off *M. quartrifoliata* while saving 25 kg N/ha, as previously reported. ■

Azolla manuring rectifies zinc deficiency

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai, India

Zinc deficiency is a problem in the second crop (thaladi) immediately following the first crop (kuruvai) in double-cropped wetlands in Thanjavur district of Tamil Nadu.

A trial with three replications during the 1979-80 thaladi season studied the maximum level of azolla (*A. pinnata*) application that gave a significant additional yield in the variety ADT31. The number of leaves and the intensity of leaf area affected by zinc deficiency were assessed 4 times — 20th, 25th, 30th, and 35th day after transplanting (DT) — as the zinc deficiency was observed in a severe form in the early stages of crop growth. The mean of the maximum